

FATIGUE CRACK GROWTH THROUGH COMPOSITES WITH CONTINUOUS FIBER REINFORCEMENT

David L. Davidson
Southwest Research Institute
San Antonio, Texas, USA

Abstract

Fatigue cracks have been grown through Ti-6Al-4V/SCS-6 and ARALL composites. The interface bond between matrix and fibers for both materials is sufficiently weak that fibers do not break as the fatigue crack passes. The resulting bridging of the crack by fibers is the dominant factor in controlling fatigue crack growth. This paper describes the micromechanics of crack growth in these two composites and indicates how the effects of crack bridging may be modeled to predict fatigue crack growth.

Keywords: fatigue crack growth, metal matrix composites, crack bridging, micromechanics, modeling

1. INTRODUCTION

Composites reinforced by continuous fibers that demonstrate good fatigue crack growth resistance have interfaces that are not too strong nor too weak. If the interface is strong, then crack growth is self similar, with fibers being broken as the crack tip passes. Crack growth rates may be predicted from those of the matrix material by using a modulus adjusted stress intensity factor ($\Delta K/E$). When the interface is very weak, cracks grow along the fiber-matrix interface until failure. Interfaces of intermediate strength used together with strong fibers allow passage of a fatigue crack through the material without breaking the fibers. The mechanism controlling the rate of crack growth for these materials becomes the effectiveness of the fibers bridging the crack wake. This paper reports on fatigue crack growth through two materials having interfaces of intermediate strength where crack wake bridging is the dominant mechanism controlling crack velocity. Detailed reports of fatigue crack growth through these materials have been prepared previously [1,2]; the purpose of this paper is to compare the characteristics of crack bridging in the two materials and examine a model that has been developed for predicting fatigue crack growth in materials where fiber bridging is the dominant mechanism.

2. MATERIALS

The two materials compared in this paper are ARALL-4 and Ti-6Al-4V/SCS-6. ARALL[®] (Aramid fiber Reinforced ALuminum Laminate) was conceived and patented in the Netherlands, but is being produced commercially by Alcoa in the United States. The material investigated was manufactured by Alcoa and consisted of 3 sheets of 0.283 mm thick 2024-T8 aluminum alloy sandwiched with 2 sheets of Kevlar[®] aramid fibers approximately 12 μ m in diameter embedded in epoxy resin each 0.225 mm thick, making the composite sheet a total thickness of 1.3 mm. There were approximately 1720 fibers per mm of composite in the two layers. The volume fraction of fibers was approximately 0.15 of the total composite cross-sectional area.

Textron Specialty Materials Co. of Lowell, Maine manufactured the Ti-6Al-4V titanium alloy matrix

composite using their high strength 150 μm diameter SCS-6[®] fiber, itself a composite, that is composed of CVD silicon carbide on a carbon core and sheathed with 2 outer layers of carbon rich silicon carbide. These fiber coatings provide a diffusion barrier between the titanium and silicon carbide during manufacture, and it has been found that these layers are very important to the mechanical properties of the composite. The material studied consisted of 4 layers of fibers approximately uniformly spaced with respect to both material width and thickness and having a thin layer of alloy as the outer covering, for a total thickness of 0.94 mm, giving 0.42 as the approximate volume fraction of fibers.

3. EXPERIMENTAL AND MEASUREMENT TECHNIQUES

Specimens approximately 25 mm wide by 54 mm long were tested. The specimens of ARALL were of single edge notch (SEN) configuration, while the specimens of Ti-6Al-4V/SCS-6 were center notched (CN), with crack growth perpendicular to the fiber direction. The CN configuration was used for the titanium composite to lower bending loads that might have resulted in crack growth parallel to the fibers. The notches from which cracks were started were approximately 4.5 mm long for the SEN specimen and 8 mm long (total length) for the CN specimen. The applied stresses used were appropriate to the composites, with maximum stress varying between 10 and 124 MPa for ARALL, while for the Ti-6Al-4V/SCS-6 composite, the maximum stresses used were between 118 and 180 MPa. Both composites were tested using R (minimum load/maximum load) = 0.1 and load application was at 10 Hz for ARALL and 5 Hz for the titanium composite.

Fatigue cracks were initiated under load control in laboratory air using servo-hydraulic type loading frames. Periodically, specimens were transferred to a special loading stage that fit within the scanning electron microscope (SEM) so that high spatial resolution measurements could be made. Photographs were made of the crack tip region and along the crack flank at minimum, maximum, and other appropriate load levels.

For ARALL, the load required to open the crack, i.e., the level of "crack closure," was extensively measured, while for the titanium composite, there was no crack closure; the crack was found to be permanently open at minimum load, so for this material, the residual crack opening displacement (CODr) was measured. An effort was made to expose fibers in each of the materials, but for ARALL no way was found to remove the epoxy without damaging the fibers. Ion etching and electropolishing were used to make small "ports" through the outer covering of the titanium composite, thereby exposing a tiny part of the first row of SCS-6 fibers. These ports were kept as small as possible in order to cause a minimum disturbance of the residual stresses. Location of these ports was close to the line of the crack and extended ahead of, as well as behind, the crack tip.

Crack opening displacements (COD) and the displacements in SCS-6 fibers caused by loading were measured using an automated stereoisaging technique [3]. Strains were calculated as gradients of displacements.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1. Crack Growth Rates

Crack growth rates and fatigue crack closure were the principal measurements made for ARALL, although photographs of the crack tip region were also made at minimum and maximum loads. At low values of ΔK , crack growth rates were very similar to the unreinforced aluminum matrix alloy, as may be seen in **Figure 1**, where ΔK was computed from crack length and remotely applied stress as if the specimen was a solid block of aluminum alloy. The differences in crack growth rates between specimens 1 and 3 at $\Delta K < 10 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ may be attributed to differences in starting values of ΔK .

The remarkable effect of crack bridging for ARALL may be seen in the divergence in crack growth rates between the composite and the matrix alloy for ΔK above about $10 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$. The fracture toughness of the unreinforced matrix alloy is about $30 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$, but the composite was still in one piece for $K \approx 100 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$. However, at all the stresses used in the tests, increasing crack length resulted in increased growth rate.

Figure 1. Fatigue crack growth through ARALL. Data from [1].

The titanium composite exhibited even more remarkable crack growth rate behavior than ARALL. For applied maximum stresses below a level of about 170 MPa, cracks would grow with decreasing rate until they stopped growing completely. Only if stress was raised would the cracks start growing again. This behavior is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Fatigue crack growth through titanium matrix composite. Data from [2].

3.2. Fiber Stresses and Damage

Fiber stresses for the titanium composite were derived from measured displacements using the modulus for SiC. It was not possible to make measurements from fibers in ARALL because they could be accessed only through the open crack and they charged under the electron beam. Normally this problem would have been avoided by vacuum deposition of a metallic layer, but no way was devised to do this down in the crack. Fiber stresses in the titanium composite are shown in Figure 3 as a function of location relative to the crack tip. The large error bars shown reflect both the experimental error likely for these measurements and the lack of uniform strain observed within the fibers in some cases. The data of Figure 3 lead to the very important conclusion that fiber stress did not vary systematically with distance to the crack tip.

Figure 3. Stress in SCS-6 fibers as a function of distance from the crack tip. Numbers opposite symbols refer to the number of cycles - see ref. [2]

Fibers were debonded from the matrix for both composites by passage of the crack. Damage to the fibers in the titanium composite consisted of complete fiber fracture and fragmentation of the outer carbon-rich coatings in the region near the crack plane for unfractured fibers. Broken fibers were easily detected from comparison of unloaded vs. loaded photographs of the fibers through the ports. Coating damage was determined after testing by chemical removal of the matrix. The coating was undamaged at the plane of the crack, but badly cracked and often removed on either side for distances of up to nearly 0.5 mm. The extent of fiber debonding was estimated from the damage found in the outer coating of the fibers. The extent of damage (or debonding) was a function of distance from the crack tip. The extent of debonding was correlated with the measured level of CODr.

For long cracks at the higher applied stresses in ARALL, the fibers near the notch could be seen easily at maximum load, and many of the fibers appeared to be stretched thin and in some cases, shredded. From their appearance, the load carrying capacity of these fibers must have been greatly diminished.

4. MODELS FOR CRACK GROWTH

The modeling approach used to calculate the effect of crack bridging on the crack tip stress intensity factor was formulated by Sneddon and Lowengrub in 1969. This model has been elaborated on many times in recent years, but the basic concept has not been changed. Sneddon and Lowengrub computed the crack tip stress intensity factor for a crack whose flanks were subjected to a pressure $p(x)$. The crack tip stress intensity factor, K_{tip} , as corrected by McCartney [4] to give the standard form is

$$K_{tip} = \left\{ \sqrt{4a/\pi} \right\} \int \left\{ (\sigma - p(x)) / \sqrt{a^2 - x^2} \right\} dx \quad (1)$$

where a is the crack length, x is a coordinate in the crack direction with the origin at the edge or centerline of the specimen, and σ = the remotely applied stress. This equation is usually difficult to integrate because $p(x)$ is unknown, but it is much easier to integrate when $p(x)$ is a constant. For both ARALL and the titanium composite, $p(x)$ has been assumed to be a constant (p_0) for the following reasons:

1. Measured fiber stresses were approximately constant in the wake of the crack,
2. COD increased with distance from the tip, as for fatigue cracks in unreinforced material, indicating no pressure gradient, and
3. it seems reasonable to assume that a condition of equilibrium must exist along the crack flank because of the application of many thousands of loading cycles.

The first two assumptions were derived from experimental results from the titanium composite while the third is somewhat intuitive. If the condition of force equilibrium is approximately correct for the titanium composite, and that is supported to a large extent by experimental results, then it is hypothesized that it is even more likely for ARALL because of the lower modulus and plastic-like deformation characteristics of aramid fibers [5].

When crack flank stress is assumed to be constant at p_0 , integration of equation (1) gives

$$K_{tip} = \{\sqrt{(4aF/\pi)}\} \{\sigma\pi/2 + p_0(\cos^{-1}b - \pi/2)\} \quad (2)$$

where a = crack length (SEN) or half crack length (CN), F = the geometric factor for SEN or CN specimens, σ = remotely applied stress, and b = bridging zone fraction = bridging zone length/(crack + notch length).

The crack flank stress, or pressure, can be estimated by partitioning the applied load (P) according to the cracked (P_c) and uncracked (P_{uc}) areas of the specimen. The pressure p_0 is then just P_c divided by the area of the crack. Fiber stresses can be estimated by dividing P_c by the area of fibers in the bridged portion of the crack. For the titanium composite, the validity of this procedure was examined by comparing the computed fiber stress magnitudes with those measured. The result indicated that the calculation was approximately correct, with an average difference of 0.3 GPa between all the calculated and measured stresses. The variation in stress was between 1.9 and 3.5 GPa. Because of this good agreement, it was assumed that fiber stresses in ARALL would be predicted equally well using this assumption of constant fiber stress in the bridged zone.

Bridging lengths were assumed to be the entire length of the fatigue crack for ARALL because fibers were seen in the open crack to be unbroken all the way back to the notch by observation in the SEM. Conversely, for the titanium composite, bridging was found by observation to be less than the length of the crack. Bridging length was estimated based on the number of fibers found to be broken in the layer of exposed fibers while observing the crack under load in the SEM. The number of fibers in the wake of the crack varied between 4 and 6, depending on the crack length and applied stress [2].

Comparisons between the crack growth rates measured and computed using the model are shown in **Figures 4 and 5**. The model was used to calculate a value of K_{tip} from equation (2) for the values of crack length and stress in use when crack growth rate was measured. Crack growth rates were then calculated from $da/dN = B'(K_{tip})^{s'}$, where B' and s' were determined for the matrix alloy from $da/dN = B'(\Delta K - \Delta K_{th})^{s'}$.

Figure 4. Comparison of fatigue crack growth rates measured and computed

For ARALL, the model underestimates the crack growth rate slightly for the shorter crack lengths and lower applied stresses (specimens 1 and 3), while for the highest stresses and longest crack lengths (specimen 2) crack growth rate is slightly overestimated by the model. In general, agreement is good between measured and computed values, and certainly the trends are correct. There is an additional factor for this composite that has not been considered in computing crack growth rates for this material; namely, the fibers were prestressed in tension during manufacture, which is probably the reason that the cracks remained closed at minimum stress. Perhaps if this factor were included in the model, the agreement between model and experiment would be even better.

Figure 5. Comparison of fatigue crack growth rates measured and computed

For the titanium matrix composite, the model estimates the growth rates for shorter crack lengths and lower applied stresses very well, but for the highest stress (175 MPa) and longest crack, the model overestimates the growth rates by a factor of $\approx 10^2$. The most logical explanation for this is that at 175 MPa, fibers were found to debond from the matrix ahead of the crack tip, a condition not found at lower stress, nor properly considered by the model. This debonding could be compensated for in the model when computing P_c by assuming that the crack is longer (by the debonding length) than it is actually, thereby increasing the fiber bridging stress, which causes K_{tip} , and da/dN , to be lowered.

Fatigue crack growth rate and COD were measured recently for Ti-15-3/SCS-6 [6], a composite similar to the Ti-6-4 /SCS-6 composite. A constant stress model similar to that described here and in [2] was found to best describe the results. Similar measurements were recently made from a Ti-14Al-21Nb/SCS-6 composite by Larsen [7] and the results were compared to several crack bridging theories. The constant bridging stress model fit the results best.

5. CONCLUSIONS

For the continuous fiber composites ARALL and Ti-6Al-4V/SCS-6, the effects of crack bridging on fatigue crack growth rate are effectively modeled by assuming that stress in the bridging zone is constant. This assumption greatly simplifies the formula needed to calculate the crack tip stress intensity factor, K_{tip} . Bridging stress, which is needed in the calculation, is conveniently computed by partitioning the applied load between the cracked and uncracked areas. Crack growth rates computed using this modeling approach are within a factor of 2 of those measured, except when extensive fiber debonding occurs in advance of the crack tip.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Experimental work on Ti-6Al-4V/SCS-6 and modeling on both composites was sponsored by the Office of Naval Research, Contract N00014-85-C-0206, Dr. S.G. Fishman, Scientific Monitor. Experimental work on ARALL was sponsored by General Dynamics Corp. Much of the careful experimental work was performed by John Campbell. Discussions with Dr. K.S. Chan were helpful.

6. REFERENCES

1. Davidson, D.L., Austin, L.K., *Fatigue crack growth through ARALL-4*, Fatigue Fract. Engng Mater. Struct., Vol. 14, No. 10, 1991, pp. 939-951.
2. Davidson, D.L., *The micromechanics of fatigue crack growth at 25°C in Ti-6Al-4V reinforced with SCS-6 fibers*, Met. Trans. A, Vol. 23A, 1992, pp. 865-879.
3. Franke, EA., Wenzel, D. Davidson, D.L. *Measurement of micro- displacements by machine vision photogrammetry (DISMAP)*, Rev. Sci. Instrum., Vol. 62, 1991, pp. 1270-1279.
4. McCartney, L.N., *Mechanics of matrix cracking in brittle matrix fiber reinforced composites*, Proc. R. Soc. London A, Vol. 409, 1987, pp. 329-350.
5. Allen, S.R., Roche, E.J. *Deformation behavior of Kevlar aramid fibers*, Polymer, Vol. 30, 1989, pp. 996-1003.
6. Ghoshn, L.J., Kantzos, P., Telesman, J. *Modeling of crack bridging in a unidirectional metal matrix composite*, Int. J. Fracture, Vol. 54, 1992, pp. 345-357.
7. Larsen, J.M., Materials Laboratory, Wright-Patterson AFB, Ohio, Paper presented at The Metallurgical Society Meeting, Denver, February 1992.